

EVALUATION OF INTERLEUKIN-12 AND INTERLEUKIN-4 LEVELS IN MULTIBACILLARY-TYPE LEPROSY PATIENT 12 MONTHS AFTER RIFAMPICIN OFLOXACIN MINOCYCLINE COMBINATION THERAPY: A RANDOMISED STUDY

Eman Arif Rahman^{*,1}, Sri Vitayani Muchtar^{*}, Farida Tabri^{*}, Siswanto Wahab^{*}, Anni Adriani^{*}, Arifin Seweng^{**} and Rizalinda Sjahrir[△]

^{*}Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia, ^{**}Department of Biostatistics, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia, [△]Department of Medical Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia

ABSTRACT Background: Leprosy is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. In leprosy, cell-mediated immune responses are an essential aspect of host resistance to mycobacterial infections and allegedly governed by an equilibrium between type 1 cytokines including Interleukin-12 (IL-12); with type 2 cytokines such as Interleukin-4 (IL-4). Currently, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommends three leprosy treatment regimens, one of them is Rifampicin Ofloxacin Minocycline (ROM). To date, studies on the effects of ROM on leprosy have been limited; none have accurately assessed the effects of ROM on specific immune systems, especially cytokines. **Methods:** The study was conducted by prospective research method. The sample of this research were all multibacillary (MB) type of leprosy patients according to WHO classification who had received ROM therapy and recorded as the patient at research location and had medical record previous of IL-12 and IL-4 levels. After 12 months of ROM therapy, blood samples were collected and calculated using the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) using the Quantikine® high sensitivity (HSV) kit. **Results:** There was a statistically significant increase in IL-4 after 12 months of a 3-months-ROM therapy. In contrast, the levels of IL-12 after 12 months showed significant decreases. **Conclusions:** Increased levels of IL-4 and decreased many factors can cause IL-12. Therefore, further research with closer supervision is required.

KEYWORDS: Leprosy, Rifampicin Ofloxacin Minocycline therapy, Interleukin-12, Interleukin-4

INTRODUCTION

Leprosy or Hansen's disease is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, which is an intracellular obligate bacterium. The name Leprosy was first introduced by the Norwegian physician Gerhard Armauer Hansen in 1873.[1,2]

Globally, there is an upward trend in both leprosy prevalence and the detection of new leprosy cases between 2012 and mid-2013. In Indonesia, the number of new cases detected between 2011 and 2012 appears to have slightly declined, with 20,023 cases in 2011 and 18,994 cases in 2012. Of these, most cases were MB leprosy, which was 82.7%.[3]

Copyright © 2018 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.MULTIBACILLARY-TYPE-LEPROSY-INTERLEUKINS
First Received: April 30, 2018
Accepted: May 03, 2018
Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹Eman Arif Rahman, Department of Dermatology and Venereology Faculty of Medicine Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia 90245 Phone no.: +62 853 4248 7350 Email: emanarifrahman@gmail.com

Lepromatous (multibacillary) leprosy is characterised by a low cellular immunity of Th2 humoral response, which is indicated by the production of TGF- β , IL-4, IL-5, and IL-10 and high antibody production.[4] In contrast, paucibacillary leprosy shows high cellular immunity, characterised by a Th1 immune response with production of IFN- γ , IL-2, IL-7, IL-12, IL-15, and IL-18.[5] In multibacillary leprosy, there was an inhibition of IL-12 and stimulation of IL-4 responses,[6] therefore it can not limit the growth of *M.leprae*. [7]

One of the alternative regimens recommended by WHO since 1998 is the provision of single dose Rifampicin (600 mg), Ofloxacin (400 mg), and Minocycline (100 mg) for paucibacillary-type (PB).[8,9] In another study by Setia et al. which compare multiple doses of ROM against multi-drug therapy (MDT) in MB leprosy patients did not provide sufficient data to conclude the efficacy of ROM therapy in MB leprosy and additional studies of ROM therapy on MB was required.[8]

From several studies, it appears that regarding clinical, bacteriological, and histopathological, MDT MB and ROM have the same effectiveness. Until now, the recent research on the efficacy of ROM was the analysis of interleukin-12 and interleukin-4 levels in patients with MB leprosy pre- and post- combination therapy with rifampicin ofloxacin minocycline which showed that there were no significant differences.[10] Therefore, we evaluated IL-12 and IL-4 levels, each representing Th1 and Th2 immune responses respectively in MB leprosy patients 12 months after a 3-months regimen of ROM to observe whether there were any significant changes in the immune response. The study by Dogra and colleagues on 730 MB leprosy patients in northern India who were treated with MDT for 12 months showed clinical, bacteriological, and histopathological improvement in almost all patients.[11]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Time of the Study

The study was conducted at Dr.Wahidin Sudirohusodo General Hospital, South Sulawesi Dermatology Clinic General Hospital, Thajuddin Khalid Hospital and other hospitals for sampling location, NECHRI Hasanuddin University Hospital laboratory for cytokine examination with ELISA. The study was performed 12 months after therapy.

Research Design and Variable

This was a prospective research design. The research variables consist of independent variable (ROM therapy), dependent variable (IL-12, IL-4), and control variable: (12 months after therapy)

Research Population and Sample

The samples were all MB leprosy patients (WHO Classification) who had received ROM therapy and were recorded as patients in the research location and had previous interleukin-12 and interleukin-4 medical records data, with a total of 10 samples. Patients were willing to follow the research by signing informed consent.

Method of Data Collection

All samples which meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be performed anamnesis, clinical, and bacteriological examination to be included in the study after signing informed consent. Furthermore, 3 ml of blood samples were taken and then ELISA was used to detect antigen or antibody in the sample which was used to evaluate the role of IL-12 and IL-4 on immune response in MB type leprosy. The data obtained will be analysed and reported as research results.

Technique for Data Analysis

The collected data is processed and presented in the form of tables and or graphs. Data were analysed and tested using chi-square with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

A prospective study was conducted to investigate the results of IL-12 and IL-4 levels in MB leprosy patients 12 months after ROM therapy. The research was conducted at Dermatology and Venereology Polyclinics in Hospital in Makassar, NECHRI Hasanuddin University Hospital laboratory which was held on July-December 2017. A total of 10 samples of MB-type leprosy have fulfilled the criteria for study in Makassar.

Based on the characteristics of the ten samples, all respondents were male (Table 1).

Table 1 Respondent Characteristics Based on Sex

Sex	Number of Samples	Presentation (%)
Male	10	100
Female	0	0
Total	10	100

Based on the statistic distribution of patients according to age showed that the majority of respondents (40%) aged over 49 years, while respondents aged 19-28 years and 29-38 years were the same (30%). (Table 2).

Table 2 Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Age	Number of Sample	Presentation (%)
18-28	3	30%
29-38	3	30%
39-48	0	0
≥ 49	4	40%

On pre- and post-treatment slit skin smear examination of the ten samples, most (5 people) had a total of bacilli +1, three peoples had bacilli +2, and only one had bacilli +3 before therapy. Statistically, there were no samples which had smear + after therapy. (Table 3).

Table 3 Results of examination before therapy and 12 months after three months of ROM therapy

Bacall	Number of samples	
	Before	After
+1	5	0
+2	3	0
+3	1	0
Negative	-	10

Comparison of IL-4 levels before and after ROM therapy showed that there was a significant difference in the mean IL-4

index before and after therapy with $p = 0.008$ ($p < 0.05$), indicating a statistically significant improvement. (Table 4).

Table 4 Comparison of IL-4 levels before and 12 months after three months of ROM therapy

	IL-4	
	Before	after
Mean	29.16	163.40
Median	21.24	157.44
Std.deviation	34.12	85.11
Range	5,05– 115,90	61,19– 356.65
Wilcoxon test $p=0,008$		

Comparison of IL-12 levels before and after ROM therapy showed that there was no significant difference between the mean IL-12 index before and after ROM therapy with $p = 0.066$ ($p > 0.05$) indicating a statistically significant decrease (Table 5).

Table 5 Comparison of IL-12 levels before and 12 months after three months of ROM therapy

	IL-4	
	Before	after
Mean	398,68	200.98
Median	263,28	179.99
Std.deviation	328,92	99.19
Range	133,25– 1210,8	122,18– 442,86
Wilcoxon test $p=0,066$		

Distribution of changes in IL-12 and IL-4 levels 12 months after ROM therapy showed that at the levels of IL-12 before and after ROM therapy, there were two samples which showed improvement while in 7 other samples it was decreased. At the levels of IL-4 before and after ROM therapy, nine samples showed improvement, and there was one undetectable sample of IL 4 and IL12 antibodies (Table 6).

Table 6 Distribution of changes in IL-12 and IL-4 levels 12 months after three months of ROM therapy

Variable	Number of Samples			Total
	Increase	Decrease	Not detected	
IL-4	9	-	1	10
IL-12	2	7	1	10

DISCUSSION

The number of patients included in this study was ten people who received ROM treatment. In this study, all patients are male (100%). This is consistent with the literature which suggests that

men are more likely to suffer from leprosy than women; men are more susceptible to lepromatous (MB) leprosy, so more people seek treatment.[12,13] By other epidemiological studies, whereas in Saudi Arabia the number of male patients was higher with a ratio of 3.4: 1 which is higher than the global ratio. The same results also showed from the study in Kuwait and Qatar who reported a ratio of 4.5-5.5: 1.[14]

This study showed that the most affected age group was ≥ 49 years (40%). Leprosy can affect all ages, in a study on the age variation of patients between 11-75 years old, most were found in 20-30 years' age group followed by 60-70 years' age group.[15, 16] The high incidence in adulthood and elderly may be caused by the length of the incubation period, with an average duration of 2-7 years.[12] Another explanation is that leprosy in adult populations whose living in endemic areas is often reinfection or superinfection from other subclinically infected persons but which undergo a decreases in the immune response against leprosy as time progress.[15]

In this study, it appears that the number of bacilli patients ranged from +1 to +3, indicating that these patients were in the form of borderline leprosy under leprosy immunologic spectrum, with an unstable immune system.[13] The spectrum of leprosy, which consists of fixed chronic polar and borderline forms. At the tuberculoid pole (TT), a highly cell-mediated immune (CMI) system against *M.leprae* is characterised by a T-helper1 response with interferon-gamma secretion that results in a slight bacterial load /number, fewer skin lesions, and the absence or slight antibodies produced. The lepromatous pole (LL) is characterised by the low or absence of CMI-mediated specific immunity to *M.leprae*, but the production of many antibodies, high bacterial load /amount, and skin lesions are widespread. The borderline intermediary form (borderline tuberculoid, borderline and borderline lepromatous) may indicate immunologic changes towards one of the poles.[17, 18]

The subjects of the study were patients diagnosed with MB or lepromatous type leprosy. In lepromatous leprosy, resistance is very low to withstand significant bacilli proliferation, but still capable enough to induce tissue damage by inflammation, especially on the nerve. Lepromatous leprosy is characterized by low cell-mediated immunity with the type of humoral immune response is Th-2, and mRNAs mainly producing IL-4, IL-5, and IL-10 cytokines that are thought to play a role in the non-responsiveness of immunity and failure activation of macrophage in lepromatous type leprosy, so it cannot limit the growth of bacteria.[7, 19]

Interleukin-4 is first recognised as a cytokine that plays an important role in the development of Th-2 response.[20] The ability of IL-4 to provide inhibitory effects on T-cell responses and the preferential expression of IL-4 mRNA in LL patient has been well-documented. In this study, there was no significant difference between IL-4 levels before and after ROM therapy even though there was a significant increase. A slightly different result from this study was obtained by Budiani S who studied the effect of ROM therapy three months after therapy in IL-12 and IL-4 levels. Also, a study by Bandjar FK, which examined the effect of MDT MB therapy after three months on IL-12 and IL-4. This may be caused by several factors.

First, in this study, the patient's slit skin smear ranges from +1 to +3 indicating that the patient is in borderline type with an unstable immune system.[13] Leprosy is a disease with an unstable immune system. At one extreme pole (TT) the patient exhibits a strong cellular immunity to *M.leprae* which effec-

tively limits bacterial growth through the production of local Th-1 cytokines, i.e. IL-12 and IFN- γ . At the other extreme poles (LL), characterised by widespread multibacillary disease and lack of response to M. leprae, Th2 cell activation inhibits Th1 cells, which causes defects in cellular immunity specific to M. leprae. Between the two stable polar forms, there is a borderline form with an uncertain immunological status. [21, 22] Another factor is that in this study, the subjects may have a mixed Th0 cytokine pattern.[23] In the study by Hu and Salgame using Clone of Th0 shows that Th0 also produces IFN- γ and IL-4.[24] Lastly, mast cell and basophil cell activity. In addition to having a role in IgE formation in some diseases such as bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, and parasite infections. The mast cells and basophils also produce interleukin four so that the above statement may have an effect on increased IL-4 levels after treatment even though the number of bacteria decreases.[25, 26]

The same is true for IL-12 levels which showed a significant decrease between before and after ROM therapy. Interleukin-12 is a major cytokine and is essential in response to intracellular pathogens through IFN- γ production and promotion of cell-mediated immunity.[27]

Several possibilities may explain the IL-12 decline in this study: First, leprosy has two polar forms, lepromatous leprosy tuberculoid leprosy, with a contrast cytokine profile. Interferon-gamma interleukin type-1 (IFN- γ), interleukin-2 (IL-2), and IL-12 dominate tuberculoid poles, but the Th2-like cytokine profile occurs at the lepromatous pole. Between the two polar forms is an unstable clinical and immunological form, borderline tuberculoid (BT) and borderline lepromatous (BL).[28] In this study, obtained bacilli patients ranged from +1 to +3 indicating that the patient is in type borderline with an unstable immune system.[13] Inhibition of IL-12 by other cytokines, especially by IL-10. Whereas if IL-10 is elevated then, IL-12 will show a decrease. IL-10 is a strong inhibitor of IL-12 production by inhibiting transcription of the IL-12 encoding gene as well as the induction of synthesis of a special protein.[20,29] Some conditions such as chronic inflammation of the intestine may also support the production of IL-10 by B cells.[30] The coinfecting condition between Mycobacterium tuberculosis and leishmaniasis, especially in the endemic areas of Mycobacterium may show no response to IL-12.[31] Monocyte non-responsiveness in lepromatous patients, so even though stimulated by IFN- γ , monocytes still cannot produce IL-12;[32] and lastly, the probability of IL-12 inhibition by prostaglandin E2 (PGE2). PGE2 has been shown to have the ability to induce IL-10 and suppress the production of many proinflammatory cytokines.[33] There are some limitations in this study. The sample size was limited in number due to the limited number of patients in our hospitals with previous data on IL-12 and IL-4 levels. Also, our population was not examined for other possible coexisting conditions such as parasitic infestations, allergic rhinitis, asthma, and atopic dermatitis that might also affect the cytokines examined in this study. Thus, future studies with larger sample size and screening for other systemic diseases, especially those that might affect IL-12 and IL-4 levels, need to be conducted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is grateful to many of the students and colleagues whose names appeared as co-authors in publications for help and useful discussions on curcumin research. The encouragement and support for this research by the Department of atomic

energy, the government of I, is acknowledged

AUTHORS' STATEMENTS

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Bhat RM, Prakash C. Leprosy: An overview of pathophysiology. *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Infectious Diseases*. 2012;1-6.
2. Lastória JC, Abreu MAMMd. Leprosy: review of the epidemiological, clinical, and etiopathogenic aspects – Part 1. *An Bras Dermatol*. 2014;89(2):205-18.
3. WHO. Global leprosy: update on the 2012 situation. *Weekly epidemiological record*. 2013;88(35):365-80.
4. Walker SL, Lockwood DNJ. The clinical and immunological features of leprosy. *British Medical Bulletin*. 2006;1-19.
5. Jarduli LR, Sell A, Reis PG, Sippert EÂ, Ayo C, Mazini PS, et al. Role of HLA, KIR, MICA, and Cytokines Genes in Leprosy. *BioMed Research International*. 2013;1-17.
6. Kim J, Uyemura K, Dyke MKV, Legaspi AJ, Rea TH, Shuai K, et al. A Role for IL-12 Receptor Expression and Signal Transduction in Host Defense in Leprosy. *The Journal of Immunology*. 2001;167:779-86.
7. Modlin RL. Th1-Th2 paradigm: insight from leprosy. *J Invest Dermatol*. 1994;102:828.
8. Setia MS, Shinde SS, Jerajani HR, Boivin J-F. Is there a role for rifampicin, ofloxacin and minocycline (ROM) therapy in the treatment of leprosy? *Systematic review and meta-analysis*. *Tropical Medicine and International Health*. 2011;16(12):1541–51.
9. Worobec SM. Current approaches and future directions in the treatment of leprosy. *Research and Reports in Tropical Medicine*. 2012;1(3):79–91.
10. Budiani S. Analisis Kadar Interleukin-12 Dan Interleukin-4 Pada Penderita Kusta Tipe Multibasiler Pre Dan Pasca Terapi Kombinasi Rifampisin Ofloksasin Minosiklin. Makassar: Universitas Hasanuddin; 2016.
11. Dogra S, Narang T, Kumar B. Leprosy - evolution of the path to eradication. *Indian J Med Res*. 2013;137:15-35.
12. Corrêa RdGCF, Aquino DMCd, Caldas AdJM, Amaral DKCR, França FS, Mesquita ERRBP-L. Epidemiological, clinical, and operational aspects of leprosy patients assisted at a referral service in the state of Maranhão, Brazil. *Rev Soc Bras Med Trop*. 2012;45(1):89-94.
13. Bryceson A, E.Pfaltzgraff R. *Leprosy*. London: Churchill Livingstone.; 1990.
14. Assiri A, Yezli S, Tayeb T, Almasri M, Bamgboye AE, Memish ZA. Eradicating leprosy in Saudi Arabia: Outcome of a ten-year surveillance (2003-2012). *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*. 2014;12:771-7.

15. Noordeen SK. Epidemiology of leprosy. In: Hastings R.C & Opromolla DVA, editor. *Leprosy*. 2nd. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone.; 1994.
16. Manandhar U, Adhikari RC, Sayami G. Clinico-histopathological correlation of skin biopsies in leprosy. *Journal of Pathology of Nepal*. 2013;3:452-8.
17. Madan NK, Agarwal KI, Chander R. Serum Cytokine Profile In Leprosy And Its Correlation With Clinico-Histopathological Profile. *Lepr Rev*. 2011;82:371 – 82.
18. Mizoguti DdF, Hungria EM, Freitas AA, Oliveira RM, Cardoso LPV, Costa MB, et al. Multibacillary leprosy patients with high and persistent serum antibodies to leprosy IDRI diagnostic-1/LID-1: higher susceptibility to develop type 2 reactions. *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz*. 2015;110(07):914-20.
19. Parkash O. Classification of leprosy into multibacillary and paucibacillary groups: an analysis. *FEMS Immunol Med Microbiol*. 2009;55:1-5.
20. Trinchieri G. Interleukin-12: A Proinflammatory Cytokine With Immunoregulatory Functions That Bridge Innate Resistance And Antigen-Specific Adaptive Immunity. *Annu Rev Immunol*. 1995;13:251-76.
21. James WD, Bereger TD, Elston DM. *Hansen's Disease. Andrews' Diseases Of The Skin: Clinical Dermatology*. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2016.
22. Madan NK, Agarwal KI, Chander R. Serum Cytokine Profile In Leprosy And Its Correlation With Clinico-Histopathological Profile. *Lepr Rev*. 2011;82:371-82.
23. Misra N, Murtaza A, Walker B, Narayan N, Misra RS, Ramesh V. Cytokine Profile Of Circulating T Cells Of Leprosy Patients Reflects Both Indiscriminate And Polarized T-Helper Subsets: T-Helper Phenotype Is Stable And Uninfluenced By Related Antigens Of Mycobacterium Leprae. *Immunology*. 1995;86:97-103.
24. Hu C, Salgame P. Inability of interleukin-12 to modulate T-helper 0 effectors to T-helper 1 effectors: a possible distinct subset of T cells. *Immunology*. 1999;97:84-91.
25. Haas H, Falcone FH, Holland MJ, Schramm G, Haisch K. Early interleukin 4: its role in the switch towards a Th2 response and IgE mediated allergy. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol*. 1999;119:86-94.
26. Abbas AK, Lichtman AH. *Basic Immunology Functions and Disorders of the Immune System.*: Saunders Elsevier.; 2004.
27. Steding CE, Wu S-t, Zhang Y, Jeng M-H, D.Elzey B, Kao C. The Role Of Interleukin-12 On Modulating Myeloid-Derived Suppressor Cells, Increasing Overall Survival And Reducing Metastasi. *Immunology*. 2011;133:221–38.
28. Little D, Khanolkar-Young S, Coulthart A, Suneetha S, Lockwood DNJ. Immunohistochemical Analysis Of Cellular Infiltrate And Gamma Interferon, Interleukin-12, And Inducible Nitric Oxide Synthase Expression In Leprosy Type 1 (Reversal) Reactions Before And During Prednisolone Treatment. *Infection And Immunity*. 2001;69(5):3413–7.
29. Priya VHS, Anuradha B, Gaddam SL, Hasnain SE, Murthy KJR, Valluri VL. In Vitro Levels Of Interleukin 10 (IL-10) And IL-12 In Response To A Recombinant 32-Kilodalton Antigen Of Mycobacterium Bovis Bcg After Treatment For Tuberculosis. *Clinical And Vaccine Immunology*. 2009;16(1):111–5.
30. Mizoguchi A, Mizoguchi E, Takedatsu H, Blumberg RS, Bhan AK. Chronic Intestinal Inflammatory Condition Generates IL-10-Producing Regulatory B Cell Subset Characterized By Cd1d Upregulation. *Immunity*. 2002;16:219-30.
31. Trindade MAnB, Denise Miyamoto GB, Sakai-Valente NY, Vasconcelos Co-IdM, Naafs B. Case Report: Leprosy and Tuberculosis Co-Infection: Clinical and Immunological Report of Two Cases and Review of the Literature. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2013;88(2):236–40.
32. Libraty DH, Airan LE, Uyemura K, Jullien D, Spellberg B, Rea TH, et al. Interferon γ Differentially Regulates Interleukin-12 and Interleukin-10 Production in Leprosy. *J Clin Invest*. 1997;99(2):336–41.
33. Kalinski P. Regulation of immune responses by prostaglandin E2. *J Immunol*. 2012;188:21-8.